

CROSSTALK BETWEEN CDK5 AND MEK–ERK SIGNALLING UPON OPIOID RECEPTOR STIMULATION LEADS TO UPREGULATION OF ACTIVATOR P25 AND MEK1 INHIBITION IN RAT BRAIN

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Abstract—Cyclin-dependent kinase 5 (cdk5) participates in opioid receptor signalling through complex molecular mechanisms. The acute effects of selective l-(fentanyl) and d-(SNC-80) opioid receptor agonists, as well as the chronic effects of morphine (the prototypic opiate agonist mainly acting at l-receptors), modulating cdk5 and activators p35/p25 and their interactions with neurotoxic/apoptotic factors, dopamine- and cAMP-regulated phosphoprotein of 32 kDa (DARPP-32) and extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) were quantified (Western Blot analyses) in the rat corpus striatum and/or cerebral cortex. To assess the involved mechanisms, MDL28170 was used to inhibit calpain activity and SL327 to disrupt MEK (ERK kinase)-ERK activation. Acute fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg) induced rapid (7–60 min) 2- to 4-fold increases of p25 content, without induction of cdk5/p25 pro-apoptotic c-Jun NH₂-terminal protein kinase or aberrant cleavage of poly(ADP-ribose)-polymerase-1, a hallmark of apoptosis. In contrast, fentanyl and SNC-80 stimulated cdk5-mediated p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (+116–166%; PKA inhibition) and p-Thr286 MEK1 (+21–82%; MEK inactivation), and this latter effect resulted in uncoupling of MEK to ERK signals. Calpain inhibition with MDL28170 (cleavage of p35 to p25) attenuated fentanyl-induced p25 accumulation (̳57%), but not the stimulation of p-Thr286 MEK1 or p-Thr75 DARPP-32. MEK–ERK inhibition with SL327 fully prevented fentanyl-induced p25 upregulation. Notably, chronic morphine treatment (10–100 mg/kg

for 6 days) also increased p25 content and p25/p35 ratio (and activated/inactivated MEK1) in rat brain cortex, which indicated that p25 upregulation persisted under the sustained stimulation of l-opioid receptors. The results demonstrate that the acute stimulation of opioid receptors leads to upregulation of p25 activator through a MEK–ERK and calpain-dependent pathway, and to disruption of MEK–ERK signalling by a cdk5/p35-induced MEK1 inhibition. Moreover, the effects induced by the sustained stimulation of l-receptors with morphine suggest the participation of cdk5/p25 complex in opiate-induced long-term neuroplasticity.

Key words: opioid receptors, cdk5, p25/p35, MEK–ERK, SL327, MDL28170.

INTRODUCTION

Protein kinases play a central role in the short- and long-lasting effects induced by opiates and other abused drugs, participating in the acquisition of tolerance, sensitization, and other behavioural hallmarks of drug addiction (Christie, 2008; Lee and Messing, 2008). The serine/threonine cyclin-dependent kinase 5 (cdk5), an atypical cdk member, has gained especial interest for its ability to mediate different forms of structural and behavioural plasticity (Benavides and Bibb, 2004; Angelo et al., 2006; Lai and Ip, 2009; Barnett and Bibb, 2011), including those induced by opiate drugs (Ferrer-Alcón et al., 2003; Narita et al., 2005; Xie et al., 2009). Activation of cdk5 requires its association with p35 cofactor, a non-cyclin regulatory protein mainly expressed in neurons (Tsai et al., 1994; Lew et al., 1994). In turn, calpain activity targets p35 to yield p25 (Kusakawa et al., 2000; Nath et al., 2000), a more potent and long-lasting cdk5 activator (Patrick et al., 1999). Aberrant cdk5/p25 activation was initially associated with neurotoxicity and neurodegeneration (Patrick et al., 1999; Lee et al., 2000; but also see Taniguchi et al., 2001). Recent findings, however, indicate that p25-mediated neurotoxicity is not a key feature of Alzheimer's disease (Engmann et al., 2011). The stimulation of cdk5/p35/p25 by morphine in the rodent brain in vivo is also controversial (Ferrer-Alcón et al., 2003; Contet et al., 2008). Recently, cocaine and d-amphetamine were shown to stimulate rodent striatal cdk5 through the induction of p25, which may underlie some of the neuroplastic and/or neurotoxic effects of psychostimulants (Meyer et al., 2008; Mlewski et al., 2008).

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Abbreviations: BCA, bichoninic acid; cAMP, cyclic AMP; cdk5, cyclin-dependent kinase 5; ctx, cerebral cortex; DARPP-32, dopamine- and cAMP-regulated phosphoprotein of 32 kDa; DMSO, dimethyl sulphoxide; ECL, enhanced chemiluminescence; ERK, extracellular signal-regulated kinase; i.p., intraperitoneal; JNK, c-Jun NH₂-terminal kinase or stress-activated protein kinase (SAPK); MAPK, mitogen-activated protein kinase; MEK, ERK kinase; MKP-1, MAPK phosphatase-1; NMDA, N-methyl-D-aspartate; p-, phosphorylated; PAC, phosphatase of activated cells; PARP, poly(ADP-ribose)-polymerase-1; PKA, protein kinase A; PP-1, protein phosphatase-1; s.c., subcutaneous; SDS–PAGE, dodecyl sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis; SEM, standard error of the mean; str, corpus striatum; SW, spontaneous withdrawal; t-DARPP, truncated DARPP-32.

Beyond the possible neurotoxic effects of p25 (Lee et al., 2000), cdk5/p35/p25 activation may have other important outcomes. Cdk5 phosphorylates Thr75 of dopamine- and cAMP-regulated phosphoprotein of 32 kDa (DARPP-32), which results in protein kinase A (PKA) inhibition (Bibb et al., 1999; Yger and Girault, 2011). This cdk5 activity has been shown to regulate dopaminergic and glutamatergic signals, both of which are important in the molecular mechanisms of drugs of abuse including opiates (Yger and Girault, 2011). On the other hand, cdk5 is linked to extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK), which is involved in opiate-induced neuroplasticity (Girault et al., 2007; Zhai et al., 2008; Brami-Cherrier et al., 2009). Thus, the cdk5 activator p35 is under the control of ERK-mediated transcription (Harada et al., 2001). In addition, cdk5 negatively regulates ERK activity by phosphorylating the ERK kinase MEK1 at Thr286, which results in MEK inactivation (Sharma et al., 2002; Takahashi et al., 2005). It is well established that l- and d-opioid receptors can inhibit cAMP production and induce p-ERK1/2, simultaneously, in cell culture systems (Audet et al., 2008). Although opioid receptors also transduce signals through the activation of the ERK pathway in vivo, substantial discrepancies have been reported concerning the acute effects of opiate drugs in the brain. Thus, acute morphine (10 mg/kg, 20–30 min) has been shown to either downregulate or upregulate ERK activation in the mouse nucleus accumbens (Eitan et al., 2003; Valjent et al., 2004). Paradoxically, acute swim stress in rats was reported to induce a marked stimulation of MEK without the concomitant activation of ERK in various brain regions (Shen et al., 2004).

The present study was designed to unravel the existence of functional interactions between cdk5/p35/p25, neurotoxic/apoptotic signalling, DARPP-32/truncated (t)-DARPP, and/or MEK–ERK pathways modulating the acute effects of opiate agonists that selectively stimulate l- or d-opioid receptors (i.e. fentanyl and SNC-80, respectively) in the rat brain. The chronic effect of morphine, the prototypic opiate agonist acting at l-receptors, was also investigated to assess the possible involvement of cdk5/p35/p25 and MEK in opiate dependence and withdrawal. The major findings indicate that opiate agonists rapidly promote the crosstalk of cdk5 and MEK–ERK at two different points of their signalling cascades: first, p25 content is markedly upregulated by a MEK–ERK and calpain-dependent mechanism; second, MEK to ERK signal is attenuated by cdk5/p35-induced MEK1 inhibition. Moreover, chronic morphine also upregulated p25 and activated/inactivated MEK in rat brain cortex, indicating lack of tachyphylaxia to these targets upon the sustained stimulation of l-receptors. These functional interactions may have important roles in the neuroplasticity induced by opiate drugs.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Animals

A total number of 174 adult male Sprague–Dawley rats (200–240 g) were used (Charles River, Barcelona, Spain). The rats were housed in the animal facilities in methacrylate cages

(Panlab S.L., Barcelona) with wood shavings for nesting material (Ultrasorb, Panlab) under controlled environmental conditions of temperature (20 ± 2 °C), humidity (70%) and light/dark cycle (light period: 8:00–20:00), and they had free access to a standard diet (Panlab A04) and tap water. The animals were handled daily for at least 2 days before the neurochemical experiments to reduce stress during drug administrations. All animal care and experimental procedures were conducted according to standard ethical guidelines (European Communities Council Directive 86/609/EEC) and approved by the Local Bioethical Committee (UIB). All efforts were made to minimise the number of animals used and their suffering.

Drug treatments

Groups of randomly allocated rats were acutely treated (subcutaneous, s.c.) with the potent l-opioid receptor agonist fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg) for 7, 15, 30 and 60 min. Other rats were injected (intraperitoneal, i.p.) with the d-agonist SNC-80 (10 mg/kg) for 15, 30, and 60 min. Control rats received saline (1 ml/kg, s.c., 15–30 min) or dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO; 1 ml/kg, i.p., 15–30 min), respectively. To assess the specificity of the opioid receptor involved, groups of rats were injected with the non-selective l-antagonist naloxone (10 mg/kg, i.p.) 60 min before fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, s.c., 15 min), or with the selective d-antagonist naltrindole (5 mg/kg, i.p.) 30 min before SNC-80 (10 mg/kg, i.p., 30 min). The acute dose regimens of fentanyl and SNC-80 in rats were similar to those used in previous neurochemical studies (Asensio et al., 2006; Garcia-Fuster et al., 2008a). Other doses of fentanyl (0.01 and 0.03 mg/kg, s.c., 30 min) on brain cdk5/p35/p25 contents were also tested to assess dose-response effects.

To investigate the role of calpain-mediated effects (cleavage of p35 to p25) upon l-opioid receptor activation, the calpain inhibitor MDL28170 (50 mg/kg, i.p.) was administered alone (60 min) or 45 min before fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, s.c., 15 min). Other rats received vehicle (DMSO) followed by fentanyl as indicated. Control animals received DMSO plus saline injections. Similar doses of systemically injected MDL28170 (20–50 mg/kg) have been shown to inhibit (40–50%) calpain activity in rat brain (Markgraf et al., 1998; Wang et al., 2008; Thompson et al., 2010). To assess the involvement of ERK in the regulation of cdk5/p35/p25 signalling by fentanyl, the sequential activation of MEK–ERK was disrupted in vivo with the compound SL327 (Ramos-Miguel et al., 2010), a brain penetrating and selective inhibitor of MEK1/2 (Selcher et al., 1999). To this end, groups of rats were treated with SL327 (20 mg/kg, i.p.) alone (90 min) or 75 min before fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, s.c., 15 min). For comparison, other rats received DMSO and, 75 min later, the same dose of fentanyl. Control rats received DMSO plus saline. The dose of SL327 was chosen from previous studies that reported effective brain ERK inhibition in rat striatum and cortex (Selcher et al., 1999; Ramos-Miguel et al., 2010).

Finally, groups of rats were chronically treated with morphine (sustained stimulation of l-opioid receptors) to assess the modulation of cdk5/p35/p25 and activated/inactivated MEK in opiate dependence and during spontaneous withdrawal (SW). To this end, the rats were injected (i.p.) with morphine three times daily (at 09:00, 15:00 and 21:00 h), during six consecutive days, with escalating doses of the opiate (day 1: 10, 10 and 10 mg/kg; day 2: 10, 20 and 20 mg/kg; day 3: 20, 20 and 40 mg/kg; day 4: 40, 40 and 80 mg/kg; day 5: 80, 80 and 100 mg/kg; day 6: 100 mg/kg). Rats under this treatment protocol developed a strong morphine physical dependence, which resulted in a severe abstinence syndrome following SW (maximum behavioural scores at 24 h) (Ramos-Miguel et al., 2011). Control rats received parallel injections of saline (1 ml/kg, i.p.). After the chronic morphine treatment, the rats were left undisturbed in their home cages for 2 h (basal chronic effect) and 12 h, 24 h, 48 h, 72 h, and 96 h (SW effects). These groups of rats had been used

in a recent study that assessed the role of various signalling molecules, including the activation of ERK1/2, in the context of morphine-induced behavioural plasticity (Ramos-Miguel et al., 2011).

At the indicated times in the various experimental paradigms, the rats were killed without anaesthesia by decapitation. The brains were removed and the corpora striata (including caudate, putamen and nucleus accumbens) and the cerebral cortices were carefully dissected on ice, frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until the neurochemical assays.

Proteolytic cleavage of PARP-1

Poly(ADP-ribose)-polymerase-1 (PARP-1) is a sensor of DNA damage with major roles in DNA repair (Chaitanya et al., 2010). Possible aberrant cell death induced by fentanyl in rat corpus striatum and cerebral cortex was monitored through the cleavage of PARP-1 (PARP-1 Cleavage Detection Kit, Calbiochem, Darmstadt, Germany). PARP-1 (116 kDa) is cleaved into a specific 85 kDa fragment, which greatly counteract PARP function as a DNA-repairing enzyme (Chaitanya et al., 2010). The contents of PARP-1 and fragment were quantified by Western Blot analysis (see below; García-Fuster et al., 2008a).

Sample preparations, immunoblot assays, and quantitation of target proteins

Brain samples (corpus striatum and/or cerebral cortex; total homogenate) were prepared as previously described (García-Fuster et al., 2008a). Protein concentration was determined with the BCA Assay (Pierce Biotechnology, Rockford, IL, USA). Brain proteins (40 μg) were resolved by electrophoresis on 10% SDS-PAGE minigels (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Hercules, CA, USA), which was followed by immunoblotting standard procedures (García-Fuster et al., 2008a). Membranes were exposed (overnight incubation at 4°C) to the corresponding primary affinity-purified antibodies (Table 1) at the appropriate dilutions (1:500–1:10,000). The blots were then incubated (1 h, room temperature) with peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibodies (1:5000 dilution; Cell Signalling, Beverly, MA, USA), immersed into ECL

detection reagents (Amersham, Buckinghamshire, UK) and the signal of bound antibody was visualised by exposure to autoradiographic film (Amersham ECL Hyperfilm) for 1–20 min. To note that p25 and p-t-DARPP were quantified in the same immunoblots as those for p35 and p-Thr75 DARPP-35, respectively. However, longer exposure times were needed to visualise the truncated forms of these proteins since the abundance of p25 and t-DARPP is much lower than that of p35 and DARPP-32, respectively (see Figs. 1 and 3). The autoradiograms were quantified by densitometric scanning (GS-800 Imaging Calibrated Densitometer, Bio-Rad) of the immunoreactive bands. The amount of target proteins in brain samples of rats under the different treatment groups was compared in the same gel with that of control rats (saline or DMSO). The quantification procedure was assessed 3–6 times in different gels (each gel with different brain samples from control and drug-treated rats). Percent changes in immunoreactivity with respect to control samples (100%) were calculated for each treated rat in the various gels, and the mean value was used as a final estimate.

Data analyses and statistics

Results are expressed as means \pm SEM values. Statistical analyses were performed with the programme GraphPad Prism, version 4.0 (GraphPad Software, Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). The data were analysed using one- or, when appropriate, two-way ANOVA followed by the post hoc Bonferroni's test. All tests were two-tailed and the level of significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

Drugs and reagents

Fentanyl citrate and morphine hydrochloride were from Alcaiber S.A. (Madrid, Spain) and dissolved in 0.9% saline. SNC-80 [(+)-4-[(aR)-a-(2S,5R)-4-allyl-2,5-dimethyl-1-piperaziny]-3-methoxybenzyl]-N,N-diethylbenzamide], SL327 [a-amino-(4-aminophenylthio)-methylene-2-(trifluoromethyl)-benzeneacetonitrile] and MDL28170 [N-[N-[(phenylmethoxy)carbonyl]-L-valyl]-phenylalanyl] were from Tocris Cookson Ltd. (Avonmouth, UK) and

Table 1. Antibodies used for the detection and quantification of target proteins in rat brain

Protein	Antigen	Host	Catalogue	Batch	Company
p35/p25	Human p35 (peptide mapping C-terminal region)	Rabbit	sc-820	K0409	Santa Cruz
cdk5	Recombinant cdk5 protein	Mouse	MS-905P	905P604A	Lab Vision
p-c-jun	Human c-jun (short peptide containing p-Ser63/73)	Rabbit	sc-16312	A1805	Santa Cruz
c-jun	Murine c-jun (peptide mapping the DNA binding domain)	Rabbit	sc-44	M1604	Santa Cruz
p-JNK1/2	Human JNK (peptide containing p-Thr183/Tyr185)	Rabbit	9251	10	Cell Signalling
JNK1/2	Human JNK2 (GST fusion protein)	Rabbit	9252	6	Cell Signalling
PARP	Human PARP (215–228 residues)	Rabbit	512729	D33259	Calbiochem
p-DARPP-32	Human DARPP-32 (short peptide containing p-Thr75)	Rabbit	AB9208	JC1663916	Millipore
p-t-DARPP	Human DARPP-32 (short peptide containing p-Thr75)	Rabbit	AB9208	JC1663916	Millipore
DARPP-32	Cow DARPP-32 (residues 134–195)	Rabbit	sc-11365	K1009	Santa Cruz
t-DARPP	Cow DARPP-32 (residues 134–195)	Rabbit	sc-11365	K1009	Santa Cruz
p-Thr MEK1	Human MEK1 (short peptide containing p-Thr286)	Rabbit	9127	2	Cell Signalling
p-MEK1/2	Human MEK1 (short peptide containing p-Ser217/221)	Rabbit	9121	18	Cell Signalling
MEK1/2	Human MEK1/2 (synthetic peptide)	Rabbit	9122	6	Cell Signalling
p-ERK1/2	Human p44 MAPK (peptide containing p-Thr202/Tyr204)	Rabbit	9101	20	Cell Signalling
ERK1/2	Rat and human p42 MAPK (synthetic peptide)	Rabbit	442704	D33075	Calbiochem
MKP-1	Mouse MKP-1 (15 residues mapping C-terminal region)	Rabbit	sc-1199	L270	Santa Cruz
MKP-3	Human MKP-3 (peptide mapping C-terminal region)	Rabbit	sc-8599	B110	Santa Cruz
PAC-1	Human PAC-1 (20 residues of the C-terminal region)	Goat	sc-1620	F099	Santa Cruz
Spectrin	Chicken spectrin (a-chain purified from red blood cells)	Mouse	MAB1622	JC1668385	Millipore
b-actin	Human b-actin (2–16 residues)	Mouse	A1978	016K4817	Sigma Chemical

dissolved in DMSO. Naloxone hydrochloride and naltrindole hydrochloride were from Tocris, and dissolved in 0.9% saline. Drugs were dosed as the corresponding salt.

RESULTS

The l-agonist fentanyl and the d-agonist SNC-80 upregulate brain p25, a potent activator of cdk5

Treatment of rats with fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg) induced rapid (15–30 min) and marked

increases of p25 immunoccontent in the corpus striatum (+139% to +381%) and the cerebral cortex (+85% to +177%) (Fig. 1A, B). Fentanyl and SNC-80 (7–60 min) did not significantly alter the content of activator p35 (5–10% decreases) or cdk5 in the same brain samples (Fig. 1A, B; representative immunoblots for cdk5 in Fig. 1B). Thus, the ratio of p25 to p35, an index of cdk5 aberrant activation, was markedly increased in striatum and cortex after fentanyl (2.5–3.8-fold) and SNC-80 (2.2–5.6-fold) administration. Lower doses of fentanyl (0.01–0.03 mg/kg, 30 min) also increased, although to a lesser extent, striatal and cortical p25 content (+35% to +175%, at least $P < 0.05$). Pretreatment of rats with naloxone (10 mg/kg) or naltrindole (5 mg/kg) fully prevented the acute upregulation of striatal and cortical p25 induced by fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg) or SNC-80 (10 mg/kg), respectively (Fig. 1C).

The time courses of fentanyl on striatal and cortical p25 content were different. In the striatum, fentanyl upregulated p25 during 7–15 min (+139–234%), which was followed by a rapid decline toward control values at 30–60 min (Fig. 1A, B). In contrast, cortical p25 progressively increased from 7 min (+99%) to 60 min (+177%) after fentanyl (Fig. 1A, B). The time courses of SNC-80 on striatal and cortical p25 were very similar. SNC-80 robustly increased p25 in striatum (+356–381%) and, to a lesser extent, in cortex (+85–113%) during 15–30 min, which was followed by a rapid decline at 60 min (Fig. 1A, B).

Regulation of cdk5/p35/p25 downstream targets upon l- and d-opioid receptor stimulation

Accumulation of activator p25 in the brain can result in aberrant activation of cdk5. Therefore, alterations of downstream targets of cdk5/p35/p25 such as apoptotic factors (neurotoxicity), p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (PKA inhibition) and p-Thr286 MEK1 (MEK inactivation) were investigated after the acute administration of fentanyl or SNC-80 in rats.

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Fig. 1. (A, B) Acute effects (7–60 min) of fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, s.c.) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg, i.p.) on p35, p25 and cdk5 contents in rat striatum (str) and cerebral cortex (ctx). Circles are means \pm SEM of 4–5 rats per time point and expressed as percentage of vehicle (C; saline or DMSO)-treated animals. ANOVA for p25 detected significant differences between the groups of treatments for fentanyl in striatum [$F(4,20) = 4.9$; $P = 0.0065$] and cortex [$F(4,20) = 6.2$; $P = 0.0021$] as well as for SNC-80 in striatum [$F(3,12) = 64$; $P < 0.0001$] and cortex [$F(3,12) = 43$; $P < 0.0001$]. (B) Representative immunoblots of p35/p25, cdk5, and β -actin. (C) Upregulation of p25 induced by fentanyl (F) or SNC-80 (S) as above, and antagonism by pre-treatment (60 or 30 min) with naloxone (N; 10 mg/kg, i.p.) or naltrindole (Nt; 5 mg/kg, i.p.). Columns are means \pm SEM of 3–4 rats per group and expressed as percentage of vehicle-treated animals (C). ANOVA for p25 detected significant differences between the groups of treatments in striatum and cortex (at least $P < 0.001$). (A, C) $P < 0.05$, $^*P < 0.01$, $^{***}P < 0.001$ vs the corresponding control (C); at least $P < 0.05$ vs fentanyl (F) (ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). Bottom: representative immunoblots of p35/p25, and β -actin.

Fentanyl does not activate cdk5-mediated pro-apoptotic factors. Acute fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 7–60 min) did not activate c-Jun, a cdk5/p25 target, in rat striatum and cortex (Fig. 2A, shown as the ratio of p-Ser63/73 c-Jun to total c-Jun). The l-agonist reduced the activity of pro-apoptotic

c-Jun NH₂-terminal protein kinase (JNK1/2) in rat cortex (̳40%) but not in striatum at 60 min (Fig. 2B). Furthermore, fentanyl did not alter the proteolytic cleavage of the nuclear death substrate PARP-1, a hallmark of apoptosis, in the same striatal and cortical samples (Fig. 2C).

Fig. 2. Acute effects (7–60 min) of fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, s.c.) on the activation of (A) c-Jun and (B) JNK1/2, and (C) PARP-1 cleavage in rat brain cortex. Circles are means \pm SEM of 5 rats per time point and expressed as percentage of saline-treated animals (C). ANOVA for activated JNK1/2 detected significant differences between the groups of treatments [F(4,20) = 15; $P < 0.0001$], $^{**}P < 0.01$ vs controls (ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). Bottom (A–C): Representative immunoblots of phospho- and total c-Jun and JNK1/2, PARP and its 85 kDa fragment, and b-actin.

Fentanyl and SNC-80 stimulate p-Thr75 DARPP-32 and increase the content of anti-apoptotic t-DARPP. Acute fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 15–30 min) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg, 15–30 min) markedly stimulated p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (fentanyl: +152% to +166%; SNC-80: +116% to +149%), without altering total DARPP-32 content, in rat striatum (Fig. 3A, B). The time courses (7–60 min) for the effects of these opiate agonists on striatal p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (Fig. 3A) were strikingly similar to those observed for p25 accumulation (Fig. 1A). Fentanyl and SNC-80 also upregulated t-DARPP (fentanyl: +72% to +106%; SNC-80: +21% to +38%), a splicing variant of DARPP-32 lacking the first 36 amino acids of the protein (El-Rifai et al., 2002), and its phosphorylated form (presumably at Thr39; p-t-DARPP) to a much greater extent (fentanyl: +480% to +547%; SNC-80: +168% to +178%) in the same striatal samples (Fig. 3A, B).

Fentanyl and SNC-80 stimulate p-Thr286 MEK1 and alter MEK to ERK activation. Acute fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 15–30 min) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg, 30 min) stimulated p-Thr286 MEK1 in rat striatum (fentanyl: +21% to +35%; SNC-80: +37%) and cortex (fentanyl: +49% to +82%; SNC-80: +48%), without altering MEK1/2 content in any brain region (Fig. 4A, B). The inactivation of MEK1 (p-Thr286) induced by fentanyl was greater in cortex than in striatum (difference: 47%, $P < 0.05$) (Fig. 4A). Acute fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 7–60 min) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg, 15–60 min) induced rapid and transient activations of MEK1/2 (shown as the ratio of p-Ser217/221 MEK to total MEK) in rat striatum (fentanyl: +46% to +91%; SNC-80: +86%) and cortex (fentanyl: +50% to +104%; SNC-80: +114%) (Fig. 5A, B). In fentanyl-treated rats, the striatal upregulation of p-MEK1/2 (15–30 min) was followed by a transient activation of ERK1/2 (shown as the ratio of p-Thr202/Tyr204 ERK to total ERK) at 15 min (p-ERK1: +75%; p-ERK2: +56%) (Fig. 5A, B). In contrast, the cortical activation of p-MEK1/2 induced by fentanyl (15–30 min) did not result in ERK stimulation but instead in enzyme inhibition (p-ERK1: ̳28% to ̳56%; p-ERK2: ̳26% to ̳37%) (Fig. 5A, B). In SNC-80-treated rats, the marked stimulation of striatal and cortical p-MEK1/2 (30 min) resulted in moderate activations of ERK1/2 (p-ERK1: +40% to +61%; p-ERK2: +20% to +57%) (Fig. 5A, B). As a result, fentanyl increased the ratio of activated MEK (p-Ser217/221) to inactivated MEK (p-Thr286) in striatum (+34%, $P < 0.05$) and decreased that ratio in cortex (̳26%, $P < 0.05$). The ratio of activated to inactivated MEK was increased in the striatum and cortex of SNC-80-treated rats (+53% to +62%, $P < 0.05$). Notably, acute fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 30 min) did not alter the content of dual-specific protein phosphatases MKP-1 (a key negative regulator of ERK), MKP-3 and PAC-1 in rat brain cortex (data not shown).

Fig. 3. (A) Acute effects (7–60 min) of fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, s.c.) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg, i.p.) on phosphorylated and total forms of DARPP-32 and truncated t-DARPP contents in rat striatum. Circles are means \pm SEM of 4–5 rats per time point and expressed as percentage of vehicle (C; saline or DMSO)-treated animals. ANOVA detected significant differences between the groups of treatments for p-Thr75 DARPP-32 [fentanyl: $F(4,20) = 11$; $P < 0.0001$; SNC-80: $F(3,12) = 6.4$; $P = 0.0079$], p-t-DARPP [fentanyl: $F(4,20) = 21$; $P < 0.0001$; SNC-80: $F(3,12) = 25$; $P < 0.0001$], and t-DARPP [fentanyl: $F(4,20) = 8.1$; $P = 0.0005$; SNC-80: $F(3,12) = 11$; $P = 0.0009$]. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, and *** $P < 0.001$ vs controls (ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). (B) Representative immunoblots of phosphorylated and total forms of DARPP-32 and t-DARPP. Note that in addition to the normal p-Thr75 DARPP-32 immunoblot, an overexposed film is also shown (arrowed) for each opiate agonist to visualise and quantify p-t-DARPP protein (see Experimental Procedures).

Crosstalk between cdk5/p35/p25, DARPP-32 and MEK–ERK pathways upon μ -opioid receptor stimulation

The upregulation of p-Thr75 DARPP-32 and p-Thr286 MEK1 induced by fentanyl and SNC-80 suggested the participation of an aberrant cdk5/p25 complex activity in the brain. To further investigate the involved mechanisms, the acute effects of fentanyl on p35, p25, p-Thr75 DARPP-32 and p-Thr286 MEK1 were re-assessed after inhibition of calpain with MDL28170 or inhibition of MEK1/2 with SL327 in the brain in vivo. MDL28170 (50 mg/kg, i.p., 60 min) partially reduced the cleavage of the calpain substrate spectrin in rat striatum ($\dot{\gamma}28\%$ to $\dot{\gamma}37\%$) and cortex ($\dot{\gamma}28\%$ to $\dot{\gamma}34\%$) regardless of fentanyl treatment (Fig. 6A, B; see also Thompson et al., 2010). In turn, SL327 (20 mg/kg, i.p., 90 min) reduced the basal activation of ERK1/2 in rat striatum ($\dot{\gamma}48\%$ to $\dot{\gamma}52\%$) and cortex ($\dot{\gamma}29\%$ to $\dot{\gamma}51\%$) (Fig. 6C, D; see also Ramos-Miguel et al., 2010).

Calpain inhibition attenuates fentanyl-induced upregulation of p25 in the striatum but not in cortex. As observed (Fig. 1), acute fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 15 min) increased the

content of activator p25 in rat striatum (+257%) and cortex (+114%) (Fig. 7A, D). In striatum, MDL28170 (50 mg/kg) did not alter the basal cleavage of activator p35, but it attenuated ($\dot{\gamma}57\%$) fentanyl-induced p25 upregulation (Fig. 7A). In cortex, the interaction between MDL28170 and fentanyl was uncertain because the calpain inhibitor, by itself, increased p25 content (+131%) (Fig. 7D). MDL28170 alone or in combination with fentanyl did not alter cdk5 content (Fig. 7A, D representative immunoblots).

Calpain inhibition does not prevent fentanyl-induced upregulation of p-Thr286 MEK1 and p-Thr75 DARPP-32 in striatum and/or cortex. As observed (Fig. 4), fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 15 min) stimulated p-Thr286 MEK1 in rat striatum (+29%) and cortex (+80%) (Fig. 7B, E). Pretreatment with MDL28170 (50 mg/kg) did not block the striatal and cortical upregulation of p-Thr286 MEK1 (MEK inactivation) induced by fentanyl (Fig. 7B, E). It should be noted that calpain inhibition did not alter fentanyl-induced MEK–ERK modulations (data not shown). Also as reported (Fig. 3), acute fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 15 min) stimulated p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (+142%) (Fig. 7C) as well as p- and total t-DARPP (not shown) in

Fig. 4. (A) Acute effects (7–60 min) of fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, s.c.) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg, i.p.) on p-Thr286 MEK1 contents (MEK inactivation) in rat striatum (str) and cortex (ctx). Circles are means \pm SEM of 4–5 rats per time point and expressed as percentage of vehicle (C; saline or DMSO)-treated animals. For fentanyl, two-way ANOVA detected significant differences between treatment (main factor) and brain region [treatment: $F(4,40) = 11.3$; $P < 0.0001$; region: $F(1,40) = 7.9$; $P = 0.0075$; treatment-region: $F(4,20) = 1.3$; $P = 0.285$]. For SNC-80, one-way ANOVA detected significant differences between the groups of treatments in striatum [$F(3,12) = 10.8$; $P = 0.0010$] and cortex [$F(3,12) = 8.3$; $P = 0.0024$]. $^{\ast}P < 0.05$, and $^{\ast\ast\ast}P < 0.001$ vs controls; $P < 0.05$ vs corresponding ctx group (one- or two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). (B) Representative immunoblots of p-Thr286 MEK1 and total MEK1/2.

striatum. Pretreatment with MDL28170 (50 mg/kg) did not block the striatal upregulation of p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (inhibition of PKA) induced by fentanyl (Fig. 7C).

MEK inhibition prevents fentanyl-induced upregulation of p25 but not that of p-Thr286 MEK1 or p-Thr75 DARPP-32 in striatum and/or cortex. The MEK inhibitor SL327 (20 mg/kg, i.p., 90 min) by itself did not alter the content of p35, p25 or cdk5 in rat striatum and cortex (Fig. 8A, D; see representative immunoblots for cdk5 in Fig. 8A/D). However, SL327 fully prevented the upregulation of p25 induced by fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, 15 min) in striatum and cortex (Fig. 8A, D). In marked contrast, SL327 did not prevent the upregulation of the cdk5 substrates p-Thr286 MEK1 (inactivation of MEK) and p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (inhibition of PKA) induced by the μ -agonist in striatum and/or cortex (Fig. 8B, E, C).

Regulation of cdk5/p35/p25 and activated/inactivated MEK after chronic morphine and during spontaneous opiate withdrawal (SW)

To investigate the functional long-term relevance of the acute regulation of cdk5/p35/p25 and associated

downstream proteins by selective μ -(fentanyl) and δ -(SNC-80) opioid receptor agonists, the chronic effects of morphine, the prototypic opiate agonist mainly acting at μ -receptors, were finally assessed on selected targets.

Chronic treatment of rats with morphine (10–100 mg/kg for 6 days, and 2 h post-treatment) was also associated with a marked upregulation of p25 content (+113%) and increased p25/p35 ratio (2.2-fold) in brain cortex (Fig. 9A/B). During morphine SW (12–96 h), and in parallel with the intensity of the abstinence syndrome (see Ramos-Miguel et al., 2011), the content of cortical p25 declined gradually (12–24 h) to reach basal values (48–96 h) (Fig. 9A/B). In contrast, chronic morphine (2 h) and SW (12–96 h) did not significantly alter the content of activator p35 or cdk5 in the same brain cortex samples (Fig. 9A, B; representative immunoblots for cdk5 in Fig. 9B).

Chronic morphine administration (2 h post-treatment) was also associated with increased stimulation of p-Ser217/221 MEK1 (+49%, activated MEK) and p-Thr286 MEK1 (+65%, inactivated MEK), without altering total MEK1/2 content, in rat brain cortex (Fig. 9C/D). The ratio of activated MEK to inactivated MEK was slightly reduced in cortex (–11%, $P > 0.05$). During morphine SW (12–96 h) and similarly to p25, the stimulation of activated and inactivated MEK1 declined gradually (12–24 h) to finally reach basal values (48–96 h) (Fig. 9C/D).

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the complex functional interactions between cdk5/p35/p25, neurotoxic/apoptotic factors, DARPP-32/t-DARPP, and MEK-ERK signalling that operate in the rat brain upon the selective acute activation of μ -(fentanyl) and δ -(SNC-80) opioid receptors as well as after the sustained stimulation of μ -receptors with morphine.

Cdk5 participates in numerous forms of neuronal plasticity, including those induced by opiate drugs (Ferrer-Alcón et al., 2003; Narita et al., 2005; Xie et al., 2009). However, the mechanisms linking opioid receptors (mainly μ -receptors) and cdk5/p35/p25 and other downstream targets are poorly understood. This study demonstrates that acute fentanyl and SNC-80, through specific opioid receptor mechanisms, may strengthen cdk5 activity by increasing p25 availability in the brain (Fig. 10). In fact, the combined data for all fentanyl treatments (0.1 mg/kg, 15 min, $n = 18$) clearly indicated that the μ -agonist markedly increased p25 content in rat striatum (3.2 ± 0.2 -fold, $P < 0.0001$) and cortex (2.0 ± 0.1 -fold, $P < 0.0001$). Despite the large upregulation of p25, immunoblot analyses did not detect significant reductions of p35 after opiate exposure (5–10% decreases in p35 were quantified). Since the abundance of p35 in rat brain is much higher than that of p25, the proteolysis of a small fraction of the p35 reservoir might be sufficient to triplicate basal p25 content. Thus, fentanyl (combined data for 0.1 mg/kg, 15 min, $n = 18$) markedly upregulated p25/p35 ratio in rat brain (striatum: 3.7 ± 0.3 -fold, $P < 0.0001$; cortex: 2.1 ± 0.1 -fold, $P < 0.0001$). Notably, chronic morphine (the prototypic

Fig. 5. (A) Acute effects (7–60 min) of fentanyl (0.1 mg/kg, s.c.) and SNC-80 (10 mg/kg, i.p.) on p-MEK1/2, p-ERK1 and p-ERK2 (activated kinases) contents in rat striatum (str) and cortex (ctx). Circles are means \pm SEM of 4–5 rats per time point and expressed as percentage of vehicle (C; saline or DMSO)-treated animals. One-way ANOVA detected significant differences between the groups of treatments for activated MEK1/2 after fentanyl [str: $F(4,20) = 17$; $P < 0.0001$; ctx: $F(4,20) = 23$; $P < 0.0001$] and SNC-80 [str: $F(3,12) = 5.0$; $P = 0.0178$; ctx: $F(3,12) = 14$; $P = 0.0002$], as well as for activated ERK1 [str: $F(3,12) = 15$; $P = 0.0002$; ctx: $F(3,12) = 13$; $P = 0.0003$] and ERK2 [str: $F(3,12) = 14$; $P = 0.0003$; ctx: $F(3,12) = 11$; $P = 0.0007$] after SNC-80. For fentanyl, two-way ANOVA detected significant differences between treatment (main factor) and brain region for activated ERK1 [treatment: $F(4,40) = 12$; $P < 0.0001$; region: $F(1,40) = 48$; $P < 0.0001$; treatment region: $F(4,20) = 7.3$; $P = 0.0002$] and ERK2 [treatment: $F(4,40) = 16$; $P < 0.0001$; region: $F(1,40) = 59$; $P < 0.0001$; treatment region: $F(4,20) = 13$; $P < 0.0001$]. $^{\dagger}P < 0.05$, $^{\ddagger}P < 0.01$, and $^{\text{***}}P < 0.001$ vs controls; $^*P < 0.05$, $^{**}P < 0.01$, $^{***}P < 0.001$ vs corresponding ctx group (one- or two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). (B) Representative immunoblots of phospho- and total MEK1/2 and ERK1/2.

agonist relevant in opiate addiction) also increased p25 content and p25/p35 ratio in rat brain cortex, which indicates that p25 upregulation persisted under the sustained stimulation of l-opioid receptors. This finding suggests the participation of cdk5/p25 in morphine-induced long-term neuroplasticity. Chronic morphine in rats did not alter the content of cdk5 or p35 in brain cortex (present results), which is in line with similar negative data in various brain regions (including the prefrontal cortex) of morphine-sensitized mice (Contet et al., 2008).

An aberrant content of brain p25 (and cdk5 activity, as indicated by the increased p25/p35 ratio) might indicate the induction of neurotoxicity and/or cell death (Hisanaga and Endo, 2010; Torres-Altora et al., 2011). However, fentanyl- and SNC-80-induced p25 accumulation was not associated with concomitant increases in the activities of JNK1/2 (in fact it was downregulated) and p-Ser63/73 c-Jun, two cdk5/p25 downstream targets involved with apoptotic progress (Sun et al., 2009). Moreover, the tested opiate agonists upregulated the content of anti-apoptotic t-DARPP in the striatum (see below). Notably, the cleavage of nuclear PARP-1, a hallmark of apoptosis (Chaitanya et al., 2010), was unaltered in rat striatum and cortex. These data indicated that opiate drugs, including acute and chronic morphine, do not induce aberrant cell death in the mature brain (Fig. 10; see also García-Fuster et al., 2008a/b; Ramos-Miguel et al., 2011). Indeed, extra-analgesic doses of fentanyl (>0.1 mg/kg) were shown to

confer neuroprotection in focal cerebral ischaemia in rats (Chi et al., 2010), and SNC-80 was reported to be neuroprotective in rodents (Narita et al., 2006). Therefore, opiate-induced accumulation of p25 in the brain may serve other functions not related to neurotoxicity.

A relevant target of cdk5/p35/p25 in dopamine signaling is Thr75 of DARPP-32, whose phosphorylation by cdk5 mediates PKA inhibition (Bibb et al., 1999). Fentanyl and SNC-80 induced a transient but robust upregulation of p-Thr75 DARPP-32 in rat striatum. This indicates that the acute stimulation of l- and d-opioid receptors can dampen the PKA pathway, not only by inhibiting cAMP synthesis but also through a rapid inhibition of PKA mediated by cdk5 (Fig. 10). In agreement with this finding, l- and d-agonists were reported to prevent PKA-mediated p-Thr34 DARPP-32 upon dopamine D₁ or adenosine A_{2A} receptor stimulation in rat striatal slices (Lindskog et al., 1999). Similarly, in morphine-sensitized rats, a new opiate challenge increased p-Thr75 DARPP-32 and decreased p-Thr34 DARPP-32 in the striatum (Scheggi et al., 2004). It is noteworthy that anti-DARPP-32 antibodies can detect a truncated form of DARPP-32 named t-DARPP (El-Rifai et al., 2002) in rat striatum (see Fig. 3B), which has been associated with anti-apoptotic actions in gastrointestinal carcinomas (Belkhiry et al., 2005) and in cocaine-addicted brains (Alvaro-Bartolome et al., 2011). The increase of t-DARPP content (p- and total protein) induced by fentanyl and SNC-80 further supports the

Fig. 6. Acute effects of fentanyl (Fen or F; 0.1 mg/kg, 15 min, s.c.) on (A, B) spectrin fragmentation, and (C, D) ERK1/2 activation after pretreatment with (A, B) MDL28170 (MDL; calpain inhibition; 50 mg/kg, i.p.) or (C, D) SL327 (SL; MEK1/2 inhibition; 20 mg/kg, i.p.) in rat striatum (A, C) and cerebral cortex (B, D). Columns are means \pm SEM of 5 rats per group and expressed as percentage of vehicle-treated animals (C). ANOVA detected significant differences between the groups of treatments for spectrin fragments [striatum: $F(3,16) = 25$; $P < 0.0001$; cortex: $F(3,16) = 11$; $P = 0.0003$], activated ERK1 [striatum: $F(3,16) = 14$; $P < 0.0001$; cortex: $F(3,16) = 9.2$; $P = 0.0011$], and ERK2 [striatum: $F(3,16) = 6.7$; $P = 0.0045$]. $^*P < 0.05$, $^{**}P < 0.01$, and $^{***}P < 0.001$ vs controls; $P < 0.05$ vs Fen group (ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). Bottom (A–D): representative immunoblots of spectrin, b-, and p- and total ERK1/2.

notion of a tight PKA inhibition upon opioid receptor stimulation. Thus, t-DARPP lacks the regulatory domain that enhances PKA activity, which suggests that t-DARPP may function as a dominant PKA inhibitor (El-Rifai et al., 2002), possibly when phosphorylated by cdk5 (Fig. 10).

Cdk5/p35/p25 activity can also suppress MEK–ERK signalling through inactivation of MEK1 when phosphorylated at Thr286 by cdk5 in neurons (Sharma et al., 2002; Takahashi et al., 2005). Notably, acute fentanyl and SNC-80 also induced a transient but marked p-Thr286 MEK1 upregulation in rat cortex and striatum. Consequently, the sequential activation of MEK–ERK induced by fentanyl and SNC-80 was not fully concordant (see Fig. 5). Interestingly, the ratio of activated MEK1 (p-Ser217/221) to inactivated MEK1 (p-Thr286) further indicated the possibility of a concomitant stimulation of ERK1/2: fentanyl increased this ratio in striatum and decreased it in cortex; SNC-80 increased the ratio in both brain regions (see Figs. 4 and 5). To note that striatal MEK1/2 stimulation peaked 30 min after fentanyl administration, whereas

the downstream activation of ERK1/2 was arrested after 15 min of treatment. Note also that cdk5 can only target activated (p-Ser217/221) MEK1 (Sharma et al., 2002). Thus, after (but not before) MAPK activation, the pathway is rapidly disrupted by cdk5 at the MEK to ERK step, despite the fact that opioid receptors will continue activating Raf/MEK. This system allows short living and controlled stimulatory pulses on ERK1/2, which is of vital relevance in a living neuron. In addition, chronic morphine was associated with increases of both activated and inactivated MEK (with reduced activated/inactivated ratio) in cortex, predicting a dysregulation of ERK1/2 in morphine-dependent rats (see Ramos-Miguel et al., 2011). These findings strongly suggest that cdk5 activity may uncouple MEK to ERK signals in specific brain areas (e.g., cerebral cortex) in response to opioid receptor stimulation (Fig. 10). In fact, upregulation of cdk5 activity in transgenic mice overexpressing the activator p35 resulted in increased striatal p-Thr286 MEK1 and attenuated cocaine-induced ERK1/2 activation (Takahashi et al.,

Fig. 7. Modulation of fentanyl acute effects (Fen or F; 0.1 mg/kg, 15 min, s.c.) on (A, D) p35, p25 and cdk5, (B, E) p-Thr286 MEK1 (inactivated MEK), and (C) p-Thr75 DARPP-32 contents, by MDL28170 pretreatment (MDL; calpain inhibition; 50 mg/kg, i.p.), in rat striatum (A–C) and cerebral cortex (D, E). Columns are means \pm SEM of 5 rats per group and expressed as percentage of vehicle-treated animals (C). ANOVA detected significant differences between the groups of treatments for p25 [striatum: $F(3,16) = 28$; $P < 0.0001$]; cortex: $F(3,16) = 28$; $P < 0.0001$], inactivated MEK1 [striatum: $F(3,16) = 36$; $P < 0.0001$]; cortex: $F(3,16) = 37$; $P < 0.0001$], and p-Thr75 DARPP-32 [striatum: $F(3,16) = 25$; $P < 0.0001$]. $^{\dagger}P < 0.05$, $^{\ddagger}P < 0.01$, and $^{\text{***}}P < 0.001$ vs controls; $P < 0.01$ vs Fen group (ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). Bottom (A–E): representative immunoblots of p35/p25, cdk5, β-actin, p-Thr286 MEK1 and total MEK1/2, and p-Thr75 DARPP-32 and total DARPP-32.

2005). Other studies (Shen et al., 2004) reported that acute swim stress in rats elicited large increases in activated MEK (5-fold) without apparent stimulation of ERK in hippocampus and amygdala, and in other brain regions (e.g. striatum) there was a clear discrepancy between the magnitude of changes in activated MEK (>150-fold) and that of ERK (2-fold). These striking data (Shen et al., 2004) may also indicate that swim stress promotes cdk5-induced p-Thr286 MEK1 (inactivated MEK). In the current study fentanyl did not alter the brain content of

MAPK phosphatase-1 (MKP-1), which indicated that this key negative regulator of ERK signalling (Duric et al., 2010 and other references therein) is not involved in the observed MEK–ERK uncoupling. Other protein phosphatases inactivating MAPKs include protein phosphatase-1 (PP-1). Noteworthy, PP-1 is activated by p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (Svenningsson et al., 2004), which was shown to be upregulated in striatal samples of opiate-treated mice. Therefore, PP-1 might contribute to the rapid MEK–ERK inactivation in the striatum 60 min after the reported

Fig. 8. Modulation of fentanyl acute effects (Fen or F; 0.1 mg/kg, 15 min, s.c.) on (A, D) p35, p25 and cdk5, (B, E) p-Thr286 MEK1 (inactivated MEK), and (C) p-Thr75 DARPP-32 contents, by SL327 pretreatment (SL; MEK-ERK inhibitor; 20 mg/kg, i.p.), in rat striatum (A–C) and cerebral cortex (D, E). Columns are means \pm SEM of 5 rats per group and expressed as percentage of vehicle-treated animals (C). ANOVA detected significant differences between the groups of treatments for p25 [striatum: $F(3,16) = 54$; $P < 0.0001$; cortex: $F(3,16) = 6.6$; $P = 0.0017$], inactivated MEK1 [striatum: $F(3,16) = 27$; $P < 0.0001$; cortex: $F(3,16) = 51$; $P < 0.0001$], and p-Thr75 DARPP-32 [striatum: $F(3,16) = 65$; $P < 0.0001$]. † $P < 0.05$, and †† $P < 0.001$ vs controls; * $P < 0.05$, and ††† $P < 0.001$ vs Fen group (ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). Bottom (A–E): representative immunoblots of p35/p25, cdk5, β-actin, p-Thr286 MEK1 and total MEK1/2, and p-Thr75 DARPP-32 and total DARPP-32.

opiate treatments. It therefore appears that the strength and duration of ERK1/2 signals after opioid receptor stimulation are under the tight control of cdk5 activity (Fig. 10).

Interestingly, the time courses for the effects of fentanyl and SNC-80 on p-Thr286 MEK1 (inactivated MEK; see Fig. 4A) and p-Thr75 DARPP-32 (PKA inhibition;

Fig. 3A) were very similar to those observed for p25 accumulation in the brain (Fig. 1A). This suggested that cdk5/p25 activation could mediate the observed effects on MEK and DARPP-32. Since calpain mediates the proteolytic cleavage of p35 to p25 (Kusakawa et al., 2000; Nath et al., 2000), the effects of fentanyl were

Fig. 9. Effect of chronic morphine treatment (10–100 mg/kg for 6 days) and spontaneous withdrawal (SW; closed circles) for 2 (n = 7), 12 (n = 8), 24 (n = 8), 48 (n = 8), 72 (n = 4), and 96 (n = 4) hours on the contents of (A) p35 and p25, and (B) p-Ser217/221 MEK1/2 (activated) and p-Thr286 MEK1 (inactivated) in rat cortex. Circles are means \pm SEM of n rats per time point and expressed as percentage of the control rats (chronically saline-treated; opened circles; n = 8). ANOVA detected significant differences between the groups of treatments for p25 [F(6,40) = 5.57, P = 0.0003], activated MEK1/2 [F(6,40) = 7.51, P < 0.0001], and inactivated MEK1 [F(6,40) = 5.61, P = 0.0003]. *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, and ***P < 0.001 vs controls (ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test). (B, D) Representative immunoblots of p35/p25, cdk5, b-, p-Ser217/221 MEK1/2, p-Thr286 MEK1 and total MEK in cortical samples of control (Sal) and SW (2–96 h) rats.

re-assessed after inhibition of calpain with MDL28170 (Markgraf et al., 1998; Thompson et al., 2010). Pretreatment of rats with MDL28170 attenuated fentanyl-induced p25 accumulation in the striatum, but it failed to prevent the upregulation of p-Thr286 MEK1 and p-Thr75 DARPP-32, suggesting that these latter effects are related to cdk5/p35 activity rather than a cdk5/p25 hyperactivation (Fig. 10). The precise downstream targets associated with opiate-induced cdk5/p25 hyperactivation in the brain remain to be determined. A direct action of cdk5/p35 on their specific targets (MEK1, DARPP-32) is suggested to explain the current findings. Thus, two kinases were shown to catalyse MEK1 phosphorylation at Thr286: cdk5/p35 mainly active in postmitotic neurons (Sharma et al., 2002), and cdk1 active in mitotic cells (Rossomando et al., 1994). In turn, cdk5 is the sole kinase known to phosphorylate DARPP-32 at Thr75 (Bibb et al., 1999). Therefore, activation of cdk5/p35 complex appears to be responsible for the reported findings in brain.

Surprisingly, MDL28170 by itself increased the basal fragmentation of p35 to p25 in rat brain cortex, which

could be related to MDL28170 selectivity for calpain types (Friedrich, 2004) and/or to endogenous compensatory regulations upon calpain inhibition. In addition, opiate drugs did not increase basal spectrin fragmentation, further suggesting that opioid receptor stimulation leads to the activation of a selective population of calpains (targeting p35 but not spectrin), rather than to an increase of total calpain activity. Two main calpain types operate in the mammalian brain: I-calpain, sensitive to micromolar concentrations of Ca^{2+} , and m-calpain, which is thought to require over-physiological Ca^{2+} concentrations (Friedrich, 2004). It has also been reported that m-calpain can be activated by an ERK-mediated phosphorylation at Ser50 (Glading et al., 2004; Zadran et al., 2010), which, in the context of the current study, suggested a link between ERK and cdk5 pathways. To address this intriguing question, and due to the lack of commercially available antibodies against p-Ser50 calpain, the selective MEK inhibitor SL327 was co-administered with fentanyl in rats. Notably, SL327 fully prevented the upregulation of p25 induced by the opiate agonist in striatum and cortex. These novel findings indicate that opioid receptor stimulation can activate cdk5/p35 in a direct pathway and that calpain-mediated p35 cleavage to p25 is promoted through the MEK–ERK cascade (Fig. 10). Also notable is the fact that p-Thr286 MEK1 (inactivated MEK) was not blocked by SL327, which confirms that this inhibitory function of cdk5 is independent of p25 accumulation, and indicates that this phenomenon is not sensitive to a negative feedback ERK regulatory mechanism (Fig. 10).

Finally, it should be mentioned that cortical ERK activation in morphine-treated mice was shown to occur mainly in cells lacking I-opioid receptors, which suggests that other brain systems (i.e. N-methyl-D-aspartate,

Fig. 10. Functional interactions between cdk5/p35/p25, neurotoxic/apoptotic signalling, DARPP-32/truncated (t)-DARPP, and/or MEK–ERK pathways modulating the acute effects of the selective I-opioid receptor agonist fentanyl in the rat corpus striatum (and cerebral cortex). See Results and Discussion for details, including the acute effects of the selective d-agonist SNC-80 and the chronic effects of morphine.

NMDA, receptors) might be involved in the transactivation of MAPKs (Eitan et al., 2003). Similarly, the cannabinoid agonist WIN55212-2 transactivated ERK1/2 through a NMDA receptor-dependent mechanism (Valjent et al., 2001; Moranta et al., 2007). Therefore, the observed opiate-induced cdk5/p35/p25 and/or MEK–ERK stimulation might also occur by transactivation in cells that do not express opioid receptors. However, the cleavage of p35 to p25 is a specific neuronal process (Tsai et al., 1994) that occurs in a MEK–ERK and calpain-dependent manner (see SL327 and MDL28170 effects) most probably taking place in the same brain cell (Fig. 10).

CONCLUSION

This study unmasks two novel crosstalks between cdk5 and MEK–ERK pathways operating in the rat brain upon the acute l-(fentanyl) and d-(SNC-80) opioid receptor stimulation: (1) the potent cdk5 activator p25 is upregulated through a MEK–ERK and calpain-dependent pathway, and (2) MEK to ERK signal is disrupted by a cdk5/p35-induced MEK1 inhibition. In addition, chronic morphine (the prototypic opiate agonist mainly acting at l-receptors) also increased p25 content and p25/p35 ratio in rat brain cortex, indicating persistent opiate effects and a role of cdk5/p25 in opiate-induced long-term neuroplasticity.

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